

Some Metal(II) Complexes of Benomyl

(Mrs.) SAVINDRA RANDHAWA, B. S. PANNU and S. L. CHOPRA

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 22 June 1981, revised 30 September 1982, accepted 9 March 1984

The complexes of bivalent Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg with benomyl have been prepared and characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, ir spectra and magnetic susceptibility data. The ir spectra have shown that the ligand is bonded to the metal ion through the carbonyl oxygen and amide nitrogen. The magnetic data have been reported.

BENOMYL (I), [methyl-1-(butyl carbamoyl)-2-benzimidazole carbamate], an imidazole derivative, is widely used as a fungicide having both preventive and curative properties. The activity of the imidazole derivatives depends upon their interaction with metal ions in the biological processes. It was observed¹ that the imidazole ring has antifungal and antihistamic activities. The histidine moiety is known to coordinate with transition metal ions giving a variety of biologically important molecules including iron-heme systems. This prompted us to initiate some studies of the complexes of these compounds with the metal ions.

Experimental

All chemicals used for the preparation of the complexes are of AnalaR or chemically pure grade.

A solution of benomyl (>0.02 mol) in alcohol chloroform system (1 : 1 v/v) was added to metal chloride (0.01 mol) in the same solvent with continuous stirring. Benzene was added after concentration and refluxed for 1 h. It was again concentrated and the solid complex was isolated by the addition of alcohol-chloroform mixture. The complex was dried under vacuum and analysed by the standard methods².

The ir spectra of the complexes in nujol were taken on Perkin-Elmer model 621 spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility data were obtained by the Gouy method at room temperature 24.5°.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of analytical results the general formulae of the complexes are given in Table 1. The ir spectral and magnetic data are reported in Table 2 and 1, respectively.

The complexes of Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with benomyl are insoluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene, chloroform, dioxane, ether and nitrobenzene. The insolubility of the complexes

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND OTHER DATA OF THE METAL COMPLEXES*

Compd.	Colour	μ_{eff}	Analysis % ; Found/(Reqd.)	
			Metal	Chlorine
MnR ₂ Cl ₂	White	5.55	6.95 (7.71)	10.45 (10.05)
NiRCl ₂	Light green	3.07	14.30 (13.97)	16.44 (16.90)
CuRCl ₂	Mustard	2.04	14.97 (14.90)	16.56 (16.70)
ZnR ₂ Cl ₂	White	d	10.40 (9.01)	12.90 (10.00)
CdR ₂ Cl ₂	White	d	10.53 (10.62)	6.51 (6.78)
HgR ₂ Cl ₂	White	d	23.80 (23.40)	7.90 (8.32)

* All metals are bivalent.
d=diamagnetic.

indicates that these may be polymeric in nature and therefore, the electrical conductance could not be recorded.

Infrared spectra : The ir spectra (Table 2) of benomyl shows sharp absorption at 3384 cm⁻¹ (N-H stretching) due to the overlapping of vibrations of both the N-H groups of -NH-CO-OCH₃ and N-CO-NH-CH₂CH₂-CH₂ moieties. The amide-I band of -NH-CO-OCH₃ should have been lowered by the presence of NH group as it happens in normal amides but the C-OCH₃ residue is expected to exert an opposing influence as it does in the case of esters³. The carbonyl stretching frequency is

higher than that of ketones. The amide-I band of this group appears at 1742 cm^{-1} while the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of $\text{>N}-\text{CO}-\text{NHCH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$ appears at 1642 cm^{-1} . This is lower due to the presence of nitrogens of $\text{>N}-\text{CO}$ and $-\text{NH}-$ groups. The amide-II band of $-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{OCH}_3$ group having main contributions from both $\delta_{\text{N-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ along with a small contribution from $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ appears at 1608 cm^{-1} . The contribution to this from $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ of the imidazole group is also high. The amide-III band due to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ of $-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{OCH}_3$ appears at 1340 cm^{-1} (Table 2).

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1}) OF BENOMYL AND ITS COMPLEXES*

Compd.	$-\text{N}-\text{CO}-\text{NH}-$		$-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{OCH}_3$		
	$\nu_{\text{N-H}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ Amide-I	$\delta_{\text{N-H}}$ Amide-II	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ Amide-III
Benomyl (I)	3384	1642	1742	1608	1340
MnR_2Cl_2	—	1625	1700	1590	1325
NiR_2Cl_2	3485	1595	1685	1562	1312
CuR_2Cl_2	3175	1590	1676	1550	1317
ZnR_2Cl_2	3305	1625	1740	1577	1315
CdR_2Cl_2	3275	1642	1762	1598	1314
HgR_2Cl_2	3375	1649	1775	1549	1321

* All metals are bivalent.

The important ir peaks of Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} are compared with those of pure ligand. The negative shift of amide-I band of the group $-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{OCH}_3$ in case of Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} suggests the coordination through $\text{C}=\text{O}$ in these complexes. The amide-II band having main contribution from $\delta_{\text{N-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and small contribution due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ is shifted to lower frequency than that in the case of benomyl. It further shows that the ligand is coordinated through carbonyl oxygen of the $-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{OCH}_3$ and nitrogen of the imidazole group. The amide-III band shifted towards lower frequency on coordination supports the coordination through $-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{OCH}_3$ group.

The positive shift of amide-I band in case of Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} and no shift in Zn^{II} complexes, suggests no coordination of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of $-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{OCH}_3$ moiety. Amide-II and amide-III show negative band shifts suggesting that the imidazole nitrogen may be coordinated⁴.

In the case of Mn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} the lowering of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of $\text{>N}-\text{CO}-\text{NH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$

CH_3 at 1642 cm^{-1} of benomyl suggests the coordination of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group to these metal ions. But these metal ions are likely to be different from those coordinated to azo-nitrogen and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of $-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{OCH}_3$. This bonding leads to polymeric nature of the complexes. However, comparatively low shift observed in case of Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes may mean non-coordination or weak coordination of the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group. The higher $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ of Ni^{II} complex than that of pure ligand shows that the nitrogen of N-H groups is not involved in bonding with Ni^{II} . The lowering of $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ in other cases may be due to the involvement of N-H groups in hydrogen bonding. Such hydrogen bond was reported in a number of coordination compounds as in the complexes of amides with metal ions, where N-H frequency has been lowered due to hydrogen bonds and carbonyl stretching frequency has been lowered due to coordination⁵. The possibility of the coordination of the ligand through the nitrogen of $-\text{NH}-$ in case of Cd^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes cannot be ruled out.

Magnetic susceptibility measurement : Magnetic moment value of 5.55 B.M. (Table 1) for the complex $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}\text{R}_2\text{Cl}_2$ indicates the presence of five unpaired electrons. This shows that the complex is of high spin type⁶. The stereochemistry may be octahedral. The value of 3.04 B.M. for $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{R}_2\text{Cl}_2$ complex suggests the presence of two unpaired electrons. This value lies in the range 2.80-3.30 B.M. for the octahedral complexes⁷. The complex $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{R}_2\text{Cl}_2$ has been found to have the value of 2.04 B.M. The high value may be due to orbital contribution. The complexes of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} are diamagnetic.

References

1. M. PATRA, S. K. MAHAPATRA and B. DASH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **12**, 1031.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Chemistry", Longmans, New York, 1962, pp. 480-531.
3. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1966, p. 222.
4. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1963.
5. J. CHATT, L. A. DUNCANSON and L. M. VERNANZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2712.
6. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **6**, 37.
7. E. A. EARNSHAW, "Introduction to Magnetochemistry", Academic Press, London, 1969, p. 35.